

THE USE OF GRADUONYMS RELATED TO VERBS IN CHINGIZ AITMATOV'S STORY "SARVQOMAT DILBARIM"

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Abstract: On the basis of excerpts from this work, information is given about the terms of the science of semasiology. The basis of the article is graduonyms related to the verb word group. We can observe the gradation of verbs through these graduonyms.

Key words: gradual relationship, verb phrase, aspects, gradation, research methods.

In world linguistics, researches have been carried out on the issues of graduonymy, gradual relations, level categories, semantics of lexemes denoting color, importance of lexemes denoting sign in linguistics. Grammatical and semantic features, phonetic, lexical aspects, emotional-expressive functions of graduonymy were studied. Also, in recent years, the semantic development of language units in Uzbek linguistics has been studied in comparative and cross-sectional aspects. Gradual attitude is reflected in all events and processes in life, in linguistic thinking in different ways. This phenomenon is such a system that in its study, it is very important to determine the aspects of interlinguistic relations and features, the user's thinking through language, and the factors determining the evaluation.

We know that stylistic coloring of words makes speech beautiful. That is why, by using graduonyms in artistic works, we can beautifully describe the content of the work, evoke positive or, on the contrary, negative thoughts in the reader's mind. Alisher Navoi was the first among the Turkic people to study graduonymy and use it effectively, citing some examples in his work "Muhokamat-ul Lughatayn". This opened the way to learn and develop Turkish languages. In later works, the use of graduonymic examples was considered very necessary for the writer's work. Because the artistic work becomes more beautiful with literary style and colors. As for works of art, elements of graduonymy are widely used in them. They increase the artistic color of the work, expand its spiritual impact. When analyzing a work of art, graduonymic units can be included among synonyms. The units formed by the ranking become a synonymous series. In the works, such graduonymic words can be expressed by different sets of words. For example, the famous Kyrgyz writer Chingiz Aitmatov used graduonymy related to several independent word groups in his short story "Sarvqomat dilbarim". For example, in the following parts of the work, graduonyms related to the verb word group are given:

1. to run

a) For this purpose, I ran towards the stone road on the outskirts of the city. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 1)

b) A two-horse cart loaded with freshly harvested hay was moving towards the railroad crossing. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 3)

2. to ask

a) Please take me to Ribachega too! I asked the driver. (Sarvkomat dear, page 1)

b) - I beg you, I was called to Frunze on a necessary business. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 1)

3. to turn-to look-to look back

a) He turned, looked at me over his shoulder, straightened his height and calmly said: "No, brother, I can't." (Sarvkomat dear, page 1)

b) I was very dizzy, I shrugged my shoulders and looked in surprise at the old Russian woman who was quietly watching us from the window of the booth. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 1)

c) My companion did not even look back at me. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 2)

4. to hum and sing

a) It is also possible to sit in the saddle and hum a song slowly. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 2)

b) Kobiz sang about the sun setting behind the hills, about the soft breeze spreading coolness in all directions, about the blue-blue and yellow sedges that lined the road, slowly swaying and shedding flower dust. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 2)

5. To be upset

a) - I understand, but don't be upset, brother.

b) Don't be offended by me.

6. grumbling

a) "It was okay when I was in a hurry!" I grumbled, unable to bear my pain. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 2)

b) I was playing with my son... he muttered with difficulty.

7. to be worried

a) Before going down the road, he rubbed his face with his palm, sighed deeply, and looked anxiously at the road going through the mountain. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 2)

b) In the early days, I was a little cramped for some reason. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 6)

8. to smile-to smile-to laugh-to smile

a) "You must have been very upset with me then, brother?" he asked with a sad smile.

b. (Sarvqomat dilbarim, page 3)

b) "Hello, brother!" he said, smiling like a guilty person. (Sarvqamat dilbarim, page 3)

c) And he laughed. (Sarvqamat dilbarim, page 8)

d) Wearing a tattered t-shirt darkened by the sun, his pants rolled up to his knees, the stroller boy stands up, looks at the train with envy, and waves to someone while smiling.

9. shout-shout

a) "Come on, don't stand on top of me, go your way smoothly!" I shouted from under the car. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 6)

b) Do you hear me? I shouted, not knowing who I was shouting at. (Sarvkomat dear, page 7)

10. to tell - to speak - to speak

a) But I decided to tell it after listening to the driver's story to the end. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 5)

b) Because I felt it necessary to tell this detail later, at the very end of the story. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 5)

c) But I firmly believed that he would not tell anyone about his life in detail, especially me, a journalist. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 4)

11. to think - be confused

a) I thought that someone should be taken to the cabin on the way, and I asked: "What about the body?" (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 1)

b) At first, I also struggled for a long time to find ways to load more on the car. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 6)

12. to watch

a) I was very dizzy, I shrugged my shoulders and looked in surprise at the old Russian woman who was quietly watching us from the window of the booth. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 1)

b) But he was looking at me with such sincerity that I had no choice but to quickly confess. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 3)

13. argue-quarrel

a) I liked that he would always argue with me, fight, and give up immediately, even if I was wrong. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 9)

b) I liked that he would always argue and fight with me, and then give up immediately, even if I was wrong. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 9)

14. come in late - frown

a) It was getting late and it was getting dark. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 3)

b) It was getting late and it was getting dark. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 3)

15) feel-notice

a) Whether he was sad or thinking about something, it was clear from his face that there was some kind of deep sadness and indelible pain in his heart. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, p. 3)

b) Noticing that I asked an inappropriate question, I tried to divert the conversation. (Sarvqomat Dilbarim, page 4)

In this work, we can mainly observe the grading of verbs. The characteristics of stylistic painting are more perfectly expressed in them. "I loved how he would always argue with me and fight, and then give up immediately, even if I was wrong." Here, the verbs to argue and to quarrel are part of a sentence and form a graduonym. These graduation names play an important role in creating a perfect stylistic coloring of the text content. Such gradations create synonymous sequences. In most cases, this may not be the case. Because not all synonyms can form graduonyms. Among the graduonyms used in the story "Sarvqomat Dilbarim" are the synonyms of "stolen-to-look-to-look-to-stare" we can see the graded forms of the verb to look. These verbs are gradually graded from top to bottom or from bottom to top according to their use in the text. Thus, graduonymy is formed. Or the verbs to smile-to laugh-to grin-to laugh can be a clear example of this. Graduonymy in the work expresses strong and emotional signs similar to the quality levels of words. In the process of analyzing each work, special attention is paid to the meanings of the lexemes in it. (Semasiology 2008: page 85). Through these methods and methods, we can learn the characteristics and peculiarities of lexemes in the text. Because these lexemes not only show the characteristics of the text, but also embody the forms of meaning and content in it. Graduonyms have an important place not only in the fields of linguistics, but also in literature. A work without stylistic painting loses its value. This makes the reader lose interest in the work, and the text becomes like food without salt. That is why it is important to develop linguistic analysis in linguistics, to qualify the effective use of stylistic words in works, to form a positive conclusion in the student by rationally expressing the features of the lexeme in the text. In this regard, research is being carried out not only in Uzbek linguistics, but also in world linguistics.

References:

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